

1 Semi-automated classification method addressing Marine Strategy 2 Framework Directive (MSFD) zooplankton indicators

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14 Abstract

15 Semi-automated classification of zooplankton allows increasing the number of processed samples cost-effectively,
16 albeit with a relatively limited taxonomic accuracy, partly because cost-efficiency trade-off but also due to
17 technological limitations that might be overcome in the future. The present study tests the suitability of using a
18 cost-efficient semi-automated classification methodology as a tool to assess zooplankton indicators for the
19 purpose of the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive, using samples collected in the Baltic Sea. In this brackish
20 ecosystem the zooplankton individuals are small-bodied and therefore their identification with semi-automated
21 classification is challenging. However, results show that semi-automated zooplankton classification provides a
22 taxonomic classification level that is sufficient for a number of proposed indicators. This analysis also points out
23 weakness of the methodology and proposes already proved solutions based on the latest development of these
24 methodologies applied to zooplankton classification. As proved in the Baltic Sea, complementing manual
25 zooplankton analyses with the semi-automated classification offers new advantages for marine environment
26 assessment.

27 *Keywords:* MSFD, food web, zooplankton, indicators, semi-automated classification, Baltic Sea

28 Introduction

29 Protection of the marine environment is in the focus of the environmental policies all over the world, as
30 witnessed by the setting of, for instance, the Oceans Act in the USA (United States 2000) and Canada (Canada
31 1996), the National Water Act in South Africa (South Africa 1998), and the Water Framework Directive (European
32 Union 2000) and Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) (European Union 2008) in Europe (reviewed and
33 discussed by e.g. Ricketts and Harrison 2007, Barnes and McFadden 2008, Borja et al. 2008, Borja et al. 2010). The
34 main objective of these legislative initiatives is to achieve and maintain good status of marine waters, habitats

35 and resources (Borja et al. 2010). Member states of the EU are therefore required to assess the status of their
36 environment, evaluating whether it reaches good environmental status (GES) according to a list of 11 descriptors
37 of good status: (1) biodiversity, (2) non-indigenous species, (3) commercially exploited fish and shellfish, (4) food
38 webs, (5) eutrophication, (6) sea-floor integrity, (7) permanent alteration of hydrographical conditions, (8)
39 contaminants in the sea, (9) contaminants in seafood, (10) marine litter, and (11) input of energy including
40 underwater noise (European Union 2008). This evaluation is carried out using a set of specific indicators which
41 may differ between regional seas and member states, but which share some common background and
42 characteristics (European Union 2010).

43 Zooplankton has a crucial role in the pelagic food web (Checkley et al. 2009), transferring energy from primary
44 producers to fish. Changes in zooplankton abundance and biomass, taxonomic distribution, and size structure can
45 yield information about the state and dynamics of the pelagic ecosystem and food web functioning (Jeppesen et
46 al. 2011). It responds to the change of the eutrophic status of the water body (Gliwiz 1969, Pace 1986) and can
47 regulate the growth of planktivorous fish stocks (Cardinale et al. 2002, Rönkkönen et al. 2004, Rajasilta et al.
48 2014). Thus, zooplankton community structure is an important element in defining the status of the pelagic
49 ecosystem (Jeppesen et al. 2011) and is also directly or indirectly relevant to MSFD descriptors of biodiversity,
50 food webs, commercially exploited fish and shellfish, and eutrophication. Accordingly, various zooplankton
51 indicators, focusing on zooplankton size, abundance, community structure, and distribution, can be linked to
52 MSFD descriptors (Teixeira et al. 2014, Berg et al. 2015).

53 Zooplankton is monitored in most of the European seas (e.g. O'Brien 2013), and the samples are normally
54 processed by a trained analyst who identifies the zooplankton individuals to the lowest taxonomic level, sex, and
55 developmental stage, under the microscope (e.g. HELCOM 1988). A major problem with zooplankton monitoring,
56 however, is that identification and measurement of individuals in zooplankton samples are very labour intensive
57 (Benfield et al. 2007) and error rate varies for each operator or their fatigue level (Culverhouse et al. 2003,
58 Culverhouse et al. 2006), which can consequently restrict the availability of zooplankton data. However, recent
59 advances in image analysis have shown promising results for semi-automated zooplankton classification, offering
60 the possibility to complement the taxonomically accurate data with abundant data of lower taxonomic accuracy
61 and constant error rates. This methodology is based on taking a digital image of zooplankton samples by a
62 scanner (Grosjean et al. 2004) or a digital camera (Bachiller et al. 2012), and using machine learning algorithms to
63 identify the zooplankton individuals from the image, classify them into taxonomic groups (defined by the user),
64 and measuring each of these specimens separately to obtain estimates of abundance, biomass, and size spectrum
65 per taxon (Gislason and Silva 2009, Di Mauro et al. 2011). A major advantage of this methodology is that it only
66 requires inexpensive equipment and, after the initial set-up and training (Fernandes et al. 2009), it can be very
67 fast and operated by non-specialist personnel. It can estimate the zooplankton abundance and biomass from
68 large amounts of samples quickly and thus cost-effectively (Irigoiien et al. 2009, Di Mauro et al. 2011, Manríquez
69 et al. 2012), albeit with lower taxonomic accuracy (Bachiller et al. 2012). Combined with microscopy analyses, this
70 method can however provide important additional insight into the zooplankton community structure. The
71 abundant data produced by this method could also be used to develop entirely new indicators that play on the
72 strengths of this particular type of data.

73 The Baltic Sea is a semi-enclosed and shallow sea (mean depth 55 m), characterised by low salinity, strong
74 seasonality and vertical thermal and salinity stratification, partial ice-cover during winter and lack of tidal
75 movements (Leppäranta and Myrberg 2009). Salinity is regulated by river discharge and irregular saline water
76 pulses from the North Sea (Leppäranta and Myrberg 2009). Species inhabiting the Baltic Sea are mainly either of
77 marine or fresh water origin, but some true brackish water species are also found (Segerstråle 1969). Body size of
78 the Baltic zooplankton is generally smaller than in oceans (Viitasalo et al. 1995); wet weights of the most common
79 copepod and cladoceran species range between 20-130 $\mu\text{g ind}^{-1}$ (Anon. 1985). The most common Baltic copepod
80 species are *Eurytemora affinis*, *Acartia* spp., *Limnocalanus macrurus*, *Pseudocalanus elongates*, *Temora*
81 *longicornis*, and *Centropages hamatus*, whereas the most common cladocerans include *Eubosmina maritima*,
82 *Evadne nordmanni*, and *Pleopsis polyphemoides*. Due to brackish water of the Baltic Sea rotifers and cladocerans
83 are a dominant part of the zooplankton community also in the off-shore areas, while they are more coastal in
84 oceanic environments. The Baltic Sea suffers from human induced eutrophication (Raateoja et al. 2005, Fleming-
85 Lehtinen et al. 2008), which is shown to increase the small-bodied species in the zooplankton community (Pace
86 1986).

87 The present study evaluates the suitability of semi-automated zooplankton classification for zooplankton
88 indicators. The method is tested with samples from the Baltic Sea, a challenging area for the methodology due to
89 the small body size of zooplankton. This is the first study to evaluate the accuracy of the semi-automated
90 classification method for zooplankton indicators and it is the first reported Baltic Sea application.

91 Materials and methods

92 *Indicators*

93 In order to evaluate the suitability of the method for as wide range of zooplankton indicators as possible, we
94 extracted all zooplankton indicators from the MSFD indicator database compiled in 2013 (Teixeira et al. 2014,
95 Berg et al. 2015). This database, consisting of 557 biodiversity, food web, sea floor integrity, and alien species
96 indicators, mostly from Europe with some cases also from North America and the Red Sea, yielded 55
97 zooplankton indicators. In addition, in the evaluation we included newly proposed indicators from European
98 MSFD-related working group reports (ICES 2014a, 2014b). These sources provide a representative picture of the
99 main zooplankton indicator types proposed or currently used in Europe. These indicators were classified
100 according to the type of data they need as input: whether the indicator uses biomass or abundance, and what is
101 the level of taxonomic accuracy required.

102 *Sampling and sample treatment*

103 The samples were collected in August from the surface layer, during regular monitoring cruises on R/V Aranda
104 from the Gulf of Finland, northern Baltic Sea (Fig. 1), using a vertically towed 100 μm mesh sized WP-2 closing
105 plankton net (Hydrobios, Kiel, Germany). Samples were preserved immediately after collection with 4%
106 formaldehyde solution (Harris et al. 2000) until analysis in the laboratory. Before scanning, samples were dyed
107 overnight using eosin to enhance contrast (Harris et al. 2000) and applied thinly, so that the zooplankton
108 individuals were mostly separate from each other on a clear, transparent plastic tray (the lid of a PCR plate).

109 Sixteen samples were scanned two at the time using an Epson Perfection V750 scanner at 2800 dpi resolution,
110 meaning that the length of 1 mm includes approximately 110 pixels in the image. The pictures (examples in Fig. 2)
111 were scanned as colour pictures and analysed using colour picture algorithm. For the training set, 81 subsamples
112 were scanned, and a total of 1446 scanned images (zooplankton individuals and inanimate objects) of were
113 included.

114

115 Figure 1. Gulf of Finland within the Baltic Sea. The rectangle identifies the sampling area in the Gulf of Finland,
116 while the square insertion shows the Baltic Sea.

117

118 Figure 2. Examples of scanned images of various zooplankton taxa and some inanimate object classes (bubbles, fibers, and
 119 marine snow), illustrating the image quality available for the classification algorithm. The scale bars indicate the sizes of these
 120 individuals, which show in red colour because eosin dyeing is applied on the samples to enhance contrast.

121 *Semi-automated zooplankton classification*

122 The Zoolmage free software (<http://www.sciviews.org/zooimage/>) was used for semi-automated classification
 123 and measurement of individuals as well as the estimation of the biomass of individuals based on morphological
 124 measurements (Alcaraz et al. 2003). In the establishment phase, a taxonomic expert created a training set by
 125 classifying part of the images produced by the scans manually; later, zooplankton individuals (i.e. vignettes from
 126 the digitized images) were classified into predefined groups automatically based on their characteristics (see
 127 Gislason and Silva 2009 for a detailed description of the methodology, Di Mauro et al. 2011). As a result, total
 128 abundance, biomass and size spectrum were obtained for each taxon.

129 The accuracy of the method was evaluated by estimating classification error rates by 10-fold cross-validation (Bell
 130 and Hopcroft 2008) over the training set including 26 classes, 3 of which were inanimate objects (bubbles, fibres,
 131 marine snow). In other words, the training set was divided into 10 random, equal-sized fractions. Nine fractions
 132 are used for learning the classifier, which then is used to classify the tenth fraction. The process is repeated 10
 133 times, and the classification results and the true class of each image are recorded. This method simulates the
 134 situation where new, previously unseen data is fed to the classifier. The result is a matrix showing how often the
 135 individuals were classified correctly, and if they were classified incorrectly, what was the wrong class they were
 136 assigned to. If all the individuals were classified correctly, the error rate would be 0 % and accuracy 100 %.

137 The classification results were evaluated against the taxonomic resolution needs of the various types of
138 zooplankton indicators to assess whether the methodology can produce reliable data for these types of indicators
139 in the study area.

140 Results

141 *Classification results*

142 The overall error rate determined by 10-fold cross-validation was 21.8 %, but the class specific error rates varied
143 widely, from 5.3 % in small fibres to 100 % in the poorly represented Harpacticoida class (Table 1). The 26
144 categories were further grouped into 9 categories and the resulting error rates of these categories were
145 evaluated (Table 1). Most of the classification errors took place between categories within a larger taxonomic
146 group, e.g., cladocerans *Pleopsis polyphemoides* vs. *Evadne nordmanni* or copepods *Pseudocalanus spp.* vs.
147 *Temora longicornis* getting misidentified with each other. Merging categories decreased the overall error rate to
148 11.8 % and the error rates of cladocerans and copepods to 9.8 and 22.4 %, respectively (Table 1). The smallest
149 classified items were in the size range of 0.3-0.5 mm, and they could be separated to copepod nauplii and
150 combined class "small unidentified", which included both biological and inanimate small items. A relatively high
151 rate of accuracy (error rate of 4.0%) was obtained in copepod nauplii detection, meaning that only 4 % of
152 copepod nauplii individuals were misclassified in the 10-fold cross-validation.

153 Regarding inanimate objects, bubbles made up 0.6-1.7 % of the items, marine snow 3-11 % and fibres 5.5-15.5 %.
154 The error rates of these original classes were 21.1 %, 12.5 % and 5.3 %, respectively, and the error rate of the
155 combined class "inanimate" , 7.7 % (Table 1).

156

157 Table 1. Original classification with error rates and number of images per class; and the classification in which bivalves,
 158 cladocerans, copepods, and artificial and unidentified items were grouped into combined classes. The classes that have been
 159 combined are highlighted in grey. Column “n” indicates the number of individuals in this class present in the training set, and
 160 Error % gives the percentage of these individuals that were misclassified in the 10-fold cross-validation. Error 0% =
 161 determination with absolute certainty, Error 100% = every determination is unsuccessful.

Original classes	Error %	n	Combined classes	Error %	n
Appendicularia	71.43	7	Appendicularia	71.43	7
Bivalve sp. 1	50	8	Bivalves	45.45	11
Bivalve sp. 2	33.33	3			
<i>Eubosmina maritima</i>	6	100	Cladocera	9.76	369
<i>Cercopagis pengoi</i>	50	32			
<i>Daphnia</i> spp.	11.43	140			
<i>Evadne nordmanni</i>	10	50			
<i>Pleopsis polyphemoides</i>	38.3	47			
<i>Acartia</i> spp.	15.91	88	Copepoda	22.35	340
<i>Centropages</i> spp.	83.33	12			
<i>Eurytemora affinis</i>	62.5	32			
<i>Limnocalanus macrurus</i>	5.41	37			
<i>Pseudocalanus</i> spp.	80	20			
<i>Temora longicornis</i>	82.14	28			
Calanoida	36.28	113			
Cyclopoida	71.43	7			
Harpacticoida	100	3			
Copepod nauplii	4	100	Copepod nauplii	4	100
Gastropoda	33.33	3	Gastropoda	33.33	3
Polychaeta	25	8	Polychaeta	25	8
Round unidentified	58.33	12	Round unidentified	58.33	12
Small biological particles	27.5	80	Small unidentified	1.67	180
Small non-stained particles	27	100			
Bubbles	21.21	66	Inanimate	7.69	416
Marine snow	12.5	200			
Small fibers	5.33	150			
Overall error rate	21.8 %			11.8 %	

162

163 *Data needs of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive indicators*

164 The MSFD zooplankton indicators obtained from the indicator catalogue fall into 10 different types with different
 165 needs for taxonomic accuracy (Table 2), ranging from ‘no taxonomic identification’ (beyond being identified as
 166 zooplankton), to ‘identification to the species level’, including species not observed in that area previously.
 167 Examples of indicators within each type are given in Table 2. The suitability of the semi-automated classification
 168 for providing data for each of these indicator types is evaluated using the method’s ability to reliably produce the
 169 needed data as the criterion. The method can make estimations of the abundance of individuals as well as the
 170 biomass within the groups that it can distinguish reliably. Accordingly, indicators needing identification on a
 171 general taxonomic level (e.g. copepods, cladocerans) or those needing identification down to well-identified
 172 groups (e.g. reliably identified genera) can benefit from this method. On the other hand, the method would not

173 be useful for indicators needing species-level identification of all species in the sample, or for those requiring
 174 identification of previously unseen taxa (e.g. non-indigenous species).

175 Table 2. Evaluation of the suitability of semi-automated classification for three types of indicators: abundance of
 176 zooplankton, total biomass of zooplankton, and biomasses of individuals using different levels of identification.

Type of data needed for the indicator	Level of identification	Example Marine Strategy Framework Directive indicator	Suitability of semi-automated classification	Approximate error rate based on this pilot (ref. Table 1)
Abundance of zooplankton	No identification required	Abundance of zooplankton	Very good.	11.8 %
	Identified on taxonomic group level	Abundance of planktonic copepods	Possible to very good (depending on the species).	~10 - 25 %
	Identification to species/taxa level for selected taxa	Abundance ratio of selected zooplankton taxa groups	Possible to very good (depending on the taxa).	5 - 15 %
	Identification to species/taxa level for all taxa	Abundance ratio of fodder/non-fodder zooplankton	None.	5 - 80 %
	Identification to species level also concerning species previously unobserved in the area	Ratio of non-indigenous to indigenous species in plankton	None.	N/A
Total biomass of zooplankton: abundance and biovolumes of individuals	No identification required	Biomass of zooplankton	Very good.	~15 %
	Identification to taxonomic group level	Biomass of microphagous zooplankton	Possible to very good (depending on the groups).	~10 – 30 %
	Identification to species/taxa level for selected taxa	Biomass ratio of selected zooplankton taxa groups	Possible to very good (depending on the taxa).	~5 – 20 %
	Identification to species/taxa level for all taxa	Biomass ratio of non-indigenous/native species	None.	N/A
Biomasses of individuals	No identification required	Mean size of zooplankton	Very good.	N/A

177

178 In general, the semi-automated classification method is suitable for indicators which look at the total biomass or
 179 abundance or those of larger taxonomic groups (copepods, rotifers, etc.), and/or the mean size or size
 180 distribution of individuals in these groups. In contrast, indicators requiring identification of a wide range of
 181 species on a species level is not achievable under current settings and not with small sized species of the Baltic
 182 Sea.

183 Discussion

184 The data requirements for MSFD indicators consist of total abundance and total biomass of zooplankton,
 185 abundance and biomass of specific groups of zooplankton (taxonomic groups such as copepods, and functional
 186 groups such as fodder or microphagous zooplankton), abundance or biomass of both indigenous and non-
 187 indigenous zooplankton, and mean size of zooplankton individuals. Our results indicate that semi-automatic
 188 classification of zooplankton samples could provide useful data for many, but not all, of these indicator types

189 even in the challenging environment like the Baltic Sea. An overview of the strengths, weaknesses and
190 improvement possibilities described below are summarized in Table 3.

191 Table 3. Strengths, weaknesses, and improvement possibilities of semi-automated classification.

Strengths	Weaknesses	Improvement possibilities
Provides useful data for indicators that use data computed for higher taxonomic levels	Reliable classification is restricted to general taxonomic level	Reliability can be improved and error rate decreased to some degree by improving the training set by scanning hand-picked individuals identified to a certain genus/species
The size distribution and biovolume is obtained without extra effort	High error rate associated to some of the classes identified	Using a digital camera instead of a scanner would provide higher resolution and therefore allow identification of even smaller individuals
Enables effortless tracking of changes of body size within a class	Identification is only as good as the training set - if some taxa are missing or represented by only small number or poor quality images, they are not likely to be identified correctly	
Provides the possibility to obtain a quantitative estimate of certain types of microlitter (e.g. fibres)	Species previously unseen in the area (e.g. non-indigenous species) are not identified correctly	
Analysing the samples is very fast once the system is set up	Setting up the system, including building the training set, requires considerable effort	
Data-analysis is very cost-efficient		

192

193 Error rate of automatic classification system can be computed using validation methods such as 10-fold cross-
194 validation, and can be expected to remain on the same level when comparable samples are being used. While
195 human expert based microscopy analyses can be considered reliable, their error rate varies according to the
196 sample, the level of fatigue of the analyst, etc. (Culverhouse et al. 2003, Culverhouse et al. 2006). Ring tests to
197 estimate the accuracy in species identification by microscopy of different taxonomists working in the Baltic Sea
198 are regularly conducted and the results show large variation between the laboratories depending on the species
199 in question. For the management of the marine resources and environment, it is often important to know the
200 direction of change, i.e. whether the status of the sea is improving or deteriorating. Therefore, it may not be
201 important to know the exact biomass of a taxa, but rather to be confident about whether it is changing in the
202 positive direction. The known, constant error rates can help with that. In addition, knowing the error rates helps
203 to identify the indicators that are more uncertain and those that need additional effort for improvement
204 depending on how critical these are for the overall status assessment.

205 As the total abundance shows a relatively low rate of error (overall error rate of 11.8 %, Table 1), the reliability of
206 total biomass assessment depends on the biomass conversion functions. The biomasses of individuals are
207 computed based on individual measurements of equivalent spherical diameters (ESD) , converted to carbon
208 according to the conversion equation by Alcaraz et al. (2003). This additional step to transform abundance,
209 derived directly from the analysis, to biomass means that the abundance error is always lower than the biomass
210 error. However, while the body shape assumption is an approximation of the real body shape, the measurements
211 can be done reliably from the images, and the result can be assumed to reflect the true biovolume more
212 accurately than the practise of applying general sex and stage specific constant weights for all individuals, as
213 often done with data obtained by microscopic analysis (Alcaraz et al. 2003). However, due to the differences in
214 the way the individual weights are determined, the biomass results obtained from this methodology might not be
215 directly comparable with results of the microscopic analyses; biomass estimates in each methodology have their
216 own uncertainties but methodological comparisons are scarce (Hernández-León and Montero 2006). The
217 abundance and biomass estimates produced using microscopy and semi-automated classification methods could
218 be compared and the relationship between them established by studying a number of samples using both
219 methods.

220 Due to the individual measurement based biomass estimation, the semi-automated method can provide reliable
221 data for total biomass and mean size indicators. It can be used to detect changes within the mean size or size
222 distribution within a taxonomic group, giving us considerable new insight into the functioning of the zooplankton
223 community and its responses to environmental drivers. While the only type of indicator based on individual
224 biomasses present in our indicator set was body size distribution or mean size across all zooplankton taxa, it
225 would be possible to create indicators based on the body sizes of taxonomic groups, such as mean size of
226 copepods or a certain species.

227 Some of the indicators require identification to taxon level, and the applicability of the method needs to be
228 defined case by case, depending on the degree of taxa differentiation and error that can be accepted in each
229 case. Our results showed that combining the initial 26 original classes into 9 combined classes (Table 1) nearly
230 halved the total error rate from 21.8 to 11.8%. These error rates are in accordance with results from other
231 comparable studies in which error rates are reported to vary between 15-30 % with 8-53 classified groups
232 (Grosjean et al. 2004, Bell and Hopcroft 2008, Gislason and Silva 2009, Di Mauro et al. 2011, Bachiller et al. 2012).
233 We propose that based on the current results, at least the cladoceran, copepod, and copepod nauplii categories,
234 having error rates below 25 %, could be used for operational monitoring.

235 As Table 1 suggests, there is often a trade-off between taxonomic identification level and classification accuracy –
236 broader taxonomic groups can be classified with higher accuracy while more detailed taxonomic classification is
237 prone to larger errors. The classification accuracy, and which taxa get confused with each other in the
238 classification depend on the taxonomic composition of zooplankton in the area. Finding a balance between
239 sufficient taxonomic detail and classification accuracy is a question unique to each study area and dependent on
240 the purpose for which the data is used. The choice is between accepting a higher-level taxa with better

241 classification, and e.g. genus- or species-level classification with higher error rate, and which of these is preferable
242 depends on the question asked.

243 Some original classes in the present training set included only a small number of images (e.g. harpacticoid and
244 cyclopoid copepods and appendicularians), which most probably affects the classification accuracy negatively.
245 The accuracy could probably be enhanced by scanning more specimens previously identified under the
246 microscope (Bachiller et al. 2012). The advantage of such methodology is that the training set can include also
247 images that would be impossible to identify by human eye in the image. This method may provide better
248 representation of the true variability of the taxa in the community.

249 The semi-automated classification cannot identify the samples to the same taxonomic level as microscopy
250 analyses. The scanner resolution and settings also impose restrictions by setting the limit for the smallest
251 zooplankters that can be identified (Bachiller et al. 2012), which means that some taxa are unidentified by the
252 semi-automated method although they might be present in the community. Estimates of total abundance and
253 size distribution obtained are therefore restricted to individuals above the detection limit, which varies according
254 to the image quality, which can be improved by using changing the digitalization device (e.g. to a higher-
255 resolution scanner, or digital camera) (Bachiller et al. 2012). Microscopic analysis of samples is always needed to
256 support the semi-automated classification in order to guarantee the reliability of the results, improve and update
257 the training sets, and to detect unexpected events such as the appearance of non-indigenous species. On the
258 other hand, the experience in the Bay of Biscay suggests that the semi-automated classification can have
259 synergistic effects with microscopy analyses: with a higher analysis capacity provided by the semi-automated
260 classification, the demand for these analyses also increased, increasing also the demand for experts' input. While
261 the methodology requires a major investment in learning and set-up before any results are obtained, once those
262 barriers have been overcome, there is the potential to process thousands of samples and perform studies that
263 would not be possible otherwise (Irigoien et al. 2009).

264 The methodology can only classify taxa that have been included in the training set, and that provides the major
265 obstacle for identifying new non-indigenous species. In theory, however, the species that can be expected to
266 appear in the study area can be included into the training set if samples can be obtained from areas where they
267 are present. That way, their arrival to the area could be detected. The method could also in theory be improved
268 to include anomaly detection (e.g. Emmott et al. 2013), i.e. identification of individuals that do not fall into any
269 known category.

270 An error source that could jeopardize the usefulness of the semi-automated classification is the amount of
271 inanimate objects in the data, misclassified as zooplankton. Our results imply that this is not a major concern in
272 the Baltic Sea due to their relatively low amount in the samples and their small error rate, meaning that their
273 misidentification is not likely to make a significant difference in the results (Table 1). Therefore, this error source
274 is not expected to bring major bias into assessment of the total zooplankton abundance. As the inanimate objects
275 are identified with high accuracy, the method could also be used to provide a quantitative estimate of certain
276 types of microlitter (e.g. fibres) in the sea water.

277 The application in this work shows that the semi-automated classification is able to provide the required data for
278 MSFD indicators which concern total abundance or biomass of zooplankton, abundance or biomass of certain
279 taxa, and the mean size. It also provides a first error evaluation for a particularly difficult area like the Baltic Sea
280 where zooplankters are small-sized. Therefore, its final applicability depends on what is the maximum error that
281 can be accepted and whether this error can be easily reduced by increasing resources beyond this pilot study.
282 Methodological improvements that have been shown to increase the accuracy of the classification exist, the
283 drawback being that they also increase the need of personnel resources or cost of the hardware. Coordinated
284 efforts of neighbouring areas in, e.g. sharing and developing the training sets would benefit all parties and
285 guarantee better comparability of the results.

286

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